

Solvolysis of the $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{benztriazole})_2]^-$ ion in ethanol-water mixtures

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Measuring the concentration of the free thiocyanate ion and the nontransformed $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{benztriazole})_2]^-$ ion, the rate constants of the solvolysis process have been calculated. The solvolysis includes two parallel reactions – the substitution of thiocyanate ions and of benztriazole molecules. The first stage of the solvolysis is the substitution of a single SCN^- ; this reaction is of first order with regard to the complex ion. This reaction is followed by the very fast substitution of the second SCN^- . The parallel benztriazole substitution reaction seems to be a third order one, first order with regard to the complex ion and second order with regard to ethanol. The influence of the acidity has been studied.

The solvolysis of the complexes of the Reinecke salt type has not been thoroughly investigated. Adamson¹ made extensive study on the hydrolysis of $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{NH}_3)_2]^-$, but the analogous complex ions where NH_3 is substituted for different amines, remained almost unexplored. Only in one paper, Thomas and Holba² mentioned an investigation³ about the kinetics of hydrolysis in the case of the ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{aniline})_2]^-$. These authors gave no quantitative data concerning the kinetic parameters of the reaction. They mentioned only the independence of the hydrolysis rates in the pH-range 1–4.

In the present paper we report our studies on the hydrolysis of some benztriazole derivatives using ethanol-water mixtures of different compositions as solvent. As Adamson¹ observed a constant ratio between the concentration of the liberated thiocyanate ions and of the transformed complex ion, we followed the kinetics of the process measuring the concentration of the free thiocyanate ions, and the concentration versus time plots are shown in Fig. 1. As seen, the curves have no exponential shape and especially at lower temperatures can not reflect a unitary process.

Fig. 1. Variation of the free SCN^- concentration with time at different temperatures: solvent : 6.7% ethanol in water; complex concentration = 5.1×10^{-3} M.

We can assume that this reaction is more complicated than the hydrolysis of the Reinecke salt studied by Adamson. For this reason we also measured the concentration of the nontransformed complex ions in the following runs. A plot of $\log y/y_0$ vs t (where y is the actual, y_0 the initial concentration of the ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{benztriazole})_2]^-$) showed a linear variation (Fig. 2). The slope of the straight line

Table 1. Kinetic data concerning the total reaction

Solvent ethanol, wt. %	Rate constant, $k/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$					E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	log PZ	S_{298}^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	32°	42°	44.4°	47°	52°			
67.0	–	2.72	–	5.83	12.30	136.1	18.1	91.3
13.6	–	3.89	–	8.07	16.50	130.6	17.2	76.6
27.6	1.78	7.51	–	15.41	29.20	123.9	16.2	56.5
42.5	–	12.62	–	24.70	48.70	122.3	16.1	54.4
95.5	–	–	48.70	–	140.10	121.8	16.4	60.3

Fig. 2. Plots of the logarithm of the ratio : nontransformed complex concentration (y) to initial complex concentration (y_0) versus time : (a) 6.7% ethanol, 42°, (b) 27.6% ethanol, 42°, (c) 6.7% ethanol, 52°.

depends only on temperature and on the composition of the solvent and is independent of the initial concentration of the complex. This means that we have an apparently first order reaction and the corresponding rate constants can be calculated from the slope. We studied this process in ethanol-water mixtures containing 6.7, 13.6, 27.6, 42.5 and 95.5% ethanol (in weight) at temperatures 32, 42, 47 and 52°. The rate constants were calculated by least-square method. From these rate constants were calculated the activation energies E_a and $\log PZ$ factors of Arrhenius equation. For this purpose the Arrhenius equation was linearized and E_a and $\log PZ$ were obtained by means of the least-square method. Using the PZ values, the standard activation entropies were calculated according to eqn.,

$$S^\ddagger = 2.3 R \log \frac{PZh}{kT}$$

The kinetic data are presented in Table 1. The data show that the general picture is quite different from that observed by Adamson in the case of the ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{NH}_3)_2]^-$. In our case, the rate constant increases strongly with the ethanol content of the solvent, while in Adamson's experiment the rate constant was very little affected by the variation of the solvent composition, being even smaller in pure ethanol than in water.

The calculated ratio, $r = [\text{SCN}^-]/(y_0 - y)$ (free SCN^- to decomposed complex) revealed an interesting phenomenon. While in Adamson's experiments this ratio was constant with time and varied only within the limits 2.5 and 2.75 depending on the solvent composition, in the case of the analogous benzotriazole complexes we observed a very pronounced dependence of this ratio both on time and solvent composition. In our experiments r varies from 0.09 to nearly 4.0. A plot of this ratio versus the degree of transformation of the initial complex gives a single curve, characterised of the solvent concentration and independent of both temperature and initial concentration of the complex. This observation is illustrated in Fig. 3, which gives, as an ex-

Fig. 3. Plot of the ratio : free thiocyanate concentration to transformed complex concentration (r) versus the transformation degree of the complex in 27.6% ethanol.

ample, our experimental results obtained at four different temperatures in several runs carried out in the same solvent, containing 27.6% ethanol. We see that ratio r is almost constant in the first part of the solvolysis and begins to increase only when the transformation degree is already about 85%. Deviations can be observed only at the beginning of the process as the solutions contain a small amount of free thiocyanate ions even in the moment of the dissolution of the complex (the same was observed by Adamson too). The practically constant ratio, observed on the first stage of

Fig. 4. The variation of the ratio r with the transformation degree of the complex. The numbers show the ethanol content of the solvent (% in weight).

process, depends strongly on the ethanol content of the solvent. Fig. 4 shows the shape of the corresponding curves in the solvents we used.

We see from this figure that the complex undergoes a substantial transformation at high ethanol concentrations, without thiocyanate release. In these solvents the free

thiocyanate concentration begins to increase only after the disappearance of nearly the whole amount of the initial complex. As there are only benztriazole molecules besides the thiocyanate ions in the interval coordination sphere, the process of transformation observed can be only a substitution of the benztriazole molecules for solvent molecules.

The results suggest the idea of two parallel reactions. One of them, the substitution of thiocyanate ions, is little influenced by the composition of the solvent, while the rate of substitution of the benztriazole increases with the ethanol concentration. Thus, the solvolysis of thiocyanate is the preponderant process at low ethanol concentrations, but at high ethanol concentrations prevails the solvolysis of benztriazole. We consider the following stages for the solvolysis of the thiocyanate :

where ROH means the solvent molecule (water or ethanol). As in the beginning of the solvolysis the ratio r is practically constant and its value is nearly 2 at low ethanol concentration, we may presume reaction (1) being slow and reaction (2) being essentially faster, i.e. practically two thiocyanate ions are leaving the complex simultaneously. Reactions (3) and (4) become important only when ratio r begins to increase. If the solvolysis begins with the substitution of an benztriazole molecule, the first stage will be :

followed by the substitution of the other ligands.

Reactions (1) and (5) must take place simultaneously, according to our presumption, and it is possible to calculate the rate constants of both these processes from our experimental data. Considering that c is the actual concentration of the initial complex ion, k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants of reactions (1) and (5), respectively, we have the following relations :

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = -k_1 - k_5c = -kc$$

and

$$c = c_0 e^{-(k_1 + k_5)t} = c_0 e^{-kt} \quad (I)$$

This means that the experimentally observed apparent rate constant, $k = k_1 + k_5$.

Presuming that reaction (1) is followed instantaneously by reaction (2) and using eqn. (I), we can write for the free thiocyanate concentration the following equation :

$$\frac{d[\text{SCN}^-]}{dt} = 2k_1c = 2k_1c_0e^{-kt} \quad (II)$$

or integrated,

$$[\text{SCN}^-] = 2 \frac{k_1}{k} c_0 (1 - e^{-kt}) \quad (III)$$

At the same time, the concentration of the free thiocyanate can be given as

$$[\text{SCN}^-] = rc_0 (1 - e^{-kt}) \quad (IV)$$

the ratio r being practically constant at the beginning of the reaction. From eqns. (III) and (IV) we have

$$k_1 = \frac{rk}{2} \quad (V)$$

Taking into account eqn. (I), we can write rate constant of reaction (5),

$$k_5 = k \left(1 - \frac{r}{2}\right) \quad (VI)$$

The relations (V) and (VI) enable us to calculate the rate constants separately for reactions (1) and (5), using the values of the apparent rate constant k and of the ratio r . The results of our calculations are given in Tables 2 and 3. We see that k_1 varies to a small extent with the ethanol concentration; in a first approximation it can be considered as being constant. A considerable decrease is observed only in nearly pure ethanol, owing perhaps to the decrease in the water concentration. This means that the possibility of a nonzero partial order of the reaction with regard to water is not excluded. The slight increase in the rate constants with the increase in the ethanol concentration, observed at not too high ethanol concentrations, could be interpreted perhaps by the modification of the solvent structure, which could lessen the elimination of water molecules from their environment. This effect can compensate or overcompensate the decrease in the rate constant owing to the decrease in water concentration. On the basis of these consideration of S_N2 mechanism could be assumed for reaction (1).

Table 2. Rate constant of reaction (1) at different temperatures

Solvent ethanol.	Rate constant $k_1/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$			
	42°	44.4°	47°	52°
wt. %				
6.7	2.55	-	5.17	11.15
13.6	2.70	-	5.58	11.55
27.6	3.18	-	6.56	12.29
42.5	3.76	-	7.27	14.56
95.5	-	2.19	-	6.30

Table 3. Rate constant of reaction (5) at different temperatures

Solvent ethanol.	Rate constant $k_5/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$			
	42°	44.4°	47°	52°
wt. %				
6.7	0.27	–	0.83	1.13
13.6	1.19	–	2.39	4.93
27.6	4.31	–	8.88	17.21
42.5	9.03	–	17.34	32.24
95.5	–	46.5	–	133.78

For reaction (5), Table 3 shows a pronounced increase in the rate constant k_5 with increasing ethanol concentration. This allows us to presume the substitution of benzotriazole for ethanol molecules and to look for a partial reaction order with regard to ethanol. Calculating the molar concentration of ethanol in the used solvent we could observe in first approximation the constancy of the ratio $k_5/[\text{EtOH}]^2$, where $[\text{EtOH}]$ is the molar concentration of ethanol. In accordance with these results, the solvolysis of benzotriazole must be third order reaction, having the partial orders 1 and 2 with regard to the complex ion and ethanol, respectively. The rate constants obtained for this third order reaction are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Apparent rate constant of reaction (5) at different temperatures

Solvent ethanol.	Rate constant $k_1/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$			
	42°	44.4°	47°	52°
wt. %				
6.7	1.31	–	4.00	5.47
13.6	1.43	–	2.88	5.92
27.6	1.31	–	2.70	5.22
42.5	1.22	–	2.35	4.65
95.5	–	1.69	–	4.86

We calculated the activation energy and entropy of the reactions (1) and (5). The obtained values are not reliable as the results are affected by more error sources than in the case of a simple reaction. We found for the reaction (1), activation energy $E_a = 136.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and for reaction (5), $E_a = 117.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The increase in the ethanol concentration promotes reaction (5). The decrease in E_a calculated on the basis of apparent rate constants (Table 1) is thus understandable. The standard activation entropy seems to be also smaller for reaction (5) than for reaction (1). In the first case, it is nearly zero, while in the second case it is about $80 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. These values are in accordance with the assumption that reaction (5) is a third order reaction, and reaction (1) is a first or a second order one.

We also studied the influence of acidity on the kinetics

of the solvolysis. Using a solvent containing 13.6% ethanol and adding various amounts of perchloric acid, we measured the rate constants at different temperatures. The apparent rate constants, activation energy and entropy values calculated on the basis of the decrease in the complex ion concentration, are given in Table 5. The results reveal that low acid concentrations do not influence very much the total reaction rate, but when the acid concentration rises above the complex concentration, the total reaction rate increases rapidly. At the same time the activation energy and entropy decrease. A considerable decrease in ratio r is also observed. A plot of r vs transformation degree gives curves similar to those obtained at high ethanol concentrations, but the absolute value of r is smaller (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. The variation of the ratio r with the transformation degree of the complex in 13.6% ethanol at different perchloric acid concentrations. The numbers show the HClO_4 concentration in mol dm^{-3} .**Table 5.** Influence of the perchloric acid on the kinetics of the total process in ethanol 13.6% (in wt.)

Concn. $10^{-3} [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	Rate constant $k/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$			E_a kJ mol^{-1}	$\log PZ$	$S_a^{\ddagger}_{298}$ $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	42°	47°	52°			
0	3.87	8.14	16.34	130.4	17.27	77.8
1.04	–	7.47	–	–	–	–
2.08	–	7.36	–	–	–	–
4.17	4.27	9.04	16.82	124.3	16.33	57.8
8.33	5.53	–	19.42	122.2	16.02	52.2
16.67	5.96	11.46	22.68	121.3	15.92	50.0

The rate constants calculated for reactions (1) and (5) are given in Tables 6 and 7. We see that k_1 of reaction (1) decreases at higher acid concentration. At the same time, the rate constant of reaction (5) increases with the acid concentration (these results were obtained assuming the third order reaction as before). We give a quantitative explanation for this variation of the rate constants k_1 and k_5 .

Table 6. Influence of perchloric acid on the rate of reaction (1)

$10^{-3} [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	Rate constant $k_1/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	42°	47°	52°
0	2.69	5.63	11.44
4.17	0.85	1.81	3.36
8.33	0.78	—	2.93
16.67	0.71	1.38	2.72

Table 7. Influence of perchloric acid on the rate of reaction (5)

$10^{-3} [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	Rate constant $k_5/10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	42°	47°	52°
0	0.77	2.42	3.11
4.17	2.21	7.01	8.57
8.33	2.89	—	10.53
16.67	3.40	10.69	12.73

If we assume the acid ionization of the coordinated amine group of the benztriazole, it leads to the appearance of a negative charge on the nitrogen atom, which strengthens the Cr–N bond and weakens the bond between the thiocyanates and chromium ion. The addition of perchloric acid displaces the protolytic equilibrium towards the non-ionized form.

The electron-withdrawing effect of the proton weakens the Cr–N bond and k_5 increases. On the other hand, the same effect strengthens the bond between the thiocyanates and the chromium ion and consequently k_1 decreases. Thus, we must take account of two parallel processes both for reactions (1) and (5). Owing to the additivity of the rate constants of parallel reactions, the total rate constant can be written as

$$k = \alpha k' + (1 - \alpha)k^0 \quad (\text{VII})$$

where k' is the rate constant for the ionized form, k^0 that for the nonionized form and α the degree of ionization. As the degree of ionization can be given as

$$\alpha = \frac{K_a}{[\text{H}^+] + K_a} \quad (\text{VIII})$$

where K_a is the acidity constant, we can verify the accuracy of our hypothesis. For example, we can consider the k_1 data at 42° (Table 6) and taking $k_1' = 2.69 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $k_1^0 = 0.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, we can calculate K_a , using equations (VII) and (VIII). We obtain thus, for the three perchloric acid concentrations, the K_a values 4.1, 4.8 and 3.4 mol dm^{-3} , respectively. The satisfactory constancy of K_a advocates for our hypothesis.

The independence of the reaction rate of acidity, reported by Thomas and Holba² is observed in our results only at low $[\text{H}^+]$ values and only with regard to the total rate and not for the rate of the processes (1) and (5) separately. As far as the influence of the acidity on the activation energy and standard activation entropy of the total process is

concerned, the data presented in Table 5 show a systematic decrease in these values.

Fig. 6. Solubility of the oxine benztriazole in ethanol-water mixtures, at 20° .

Experimental

Synthesis of the complex : Ammonium benztriazole $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{benztriazole})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used. As the synthesis of this salt by the method of Bergmann⁴ gives very low yield, we worked out a direct synthesis. The anhyd. salt $\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_6]$ was heated at $80\text{--}90^\circ$ for 4–5 h with an excess of benztriazole (molecular ratio 1 : 4). The potassium salt of the studied complex ion was formed according to the equation,

First, the benztriazole salt (benztriazole H)[Cr(NCS)₄(benztriazole)₂] was isolated from the reaction mixture with the help of dilute acetic acid and the ammonium salt was precipitated with conc. NH_4Cl solution as reddish violet, silky, thin irregular plates (yield 85%) : $\text{NH}_4[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4(\text{benztriazole})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = 558.722$) (Found : Cr, 9.23; S, 22.82; H_2O , 3.16. Calcd. for : Cr, 9.31; S, 22.91; H_2O , 3.22%).

Kinetic measurements : The complex salt was dissolved in calculated amount of preheated ethanol and diluted with preheated water to the required volume and the solution was kept in a thermostat. Aliquots of the solution taken at various time intervals were cooled off quickly and the concentrations of free thiocyanate ion and that of the nontransformed complex were determined⁶. The free thiocyanate ion was determined photocolometrically. To the sample was added an aqueous solution of iron(III) perchlorate in excess and the absorbance of the solution was measured, using a blue filter. The corresponding concentration values were obtained with the aid of a calibration curve, plotted in the same conditions, using a standard NH_4SCN solution. The nontransformed complex was determined using a precipitation reaction with 8-quinolinol chlorohydrate. This

salt gave an insoluble product with the complex, but no insoluble compounds were formed with the solvolysis products since in the case of the SCN^- substitution either a nonelectrolytic molecule or a cation is formed, which cannot combine with the 8-quinolinolium ion, and the 8-quinolinolium salt of the product obtained by the benztriazole substitution is soluble in water. As the 8-quinolinolium benztriazole is soluble in alcohol we had to find out the conditions in which the precipitation is quantitative. For this purpose we determined the solubility of this salt in ethanol-water mixtures at 20° . As seen in Fig. 6, the solubility increases very much with the increasing ethanol content of the solvent.

Using an excess of oxine, we observed that the precipitation is quantitative in the final content of ethanol not exceeding 13% (in weight). Consequently, for the precipitation of the benztriazole ion we used a volume of aqueous oxine solution containing 1 mol 18-quinolinol and 3 mol dm^{-3} HCl, so that after the addition of this reagent the ethanol concentration was below 13%. The oxine

benztriazole was filtered and washed with distilled water. The precipitate was dissolved in methanol and the absorption of the reddish violet solution was measured photocolorimetrically using a green filter. A calibration curve was used.

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